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EDDU Protocols

DNA sequencing with the SeqStudio

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Version 2.0

EDDU-005-02

April 2020

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Version	Authors/Updated by	Date	Signature
v1.0	Michael Nicouleau	2019-05-07	
v2.0	Michael Nicouleau	2020-04-01	

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

This protocol describes how to:

- Perform a cycle sequencing of DNA using the BigDye™ Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit
- Analyse a sequencing reaction using the Applied Biosystems SeqStudio™ Genetic Analyzer

1.2 Protocol overview

Cycle sequencing can be performed directly from single or double stranded DNA, plasmid, cosmids, BACs, or purified PCR products. For high complexity DNA, PCR amplification of the target of interest before cycle sequencing is recommended.

For optimal results, PCR templates are purified before sequencing to remove excess PCR primers and unincorporated dNTPs from the reaction.

The DNA sample to be sequenced is combined in a tube with a primer, DNA polymerase, and DNA nucleotides (dNTPs). Four fluorescent dye-labeled, chain-terminating dideoxy nucleotides (ddNTPs) are added as well, but in much smaller amounts than unlabeled dNTPs nucleotides. Each ddNTP is labeled with a different coloured dye.

The mixture is first heated to denature the double-stranded template DNA, then cooled so that the primer can bind to the single-stranded template. Once the primer has bound, the temperature is raised again, allowing DNA polymerase to synthesize new DNA starting from the primer. DNA polymerase will continue adding nucleotides to the chain until it happens to add a ddNTP instead of a normal dNTP. At that point, no further nucleotides can be added, so the strand will end with the labeled ddNTP.

This process is repeated in a number of cycles. By the time the cycling is complete, it is virtually guaranteed that a ddNTP will have been incorporated at every single nucleotide position of the target DNA in at least one reaction. That is, the tube will contain fragments of different lengths, ending at each of the nucleotide positions in the original template DNA. The ends of the fragments will be labeled with fluorescent dyes that indicate their final nucleotide (ddNTP).

Next, the sequencing reaction is purified. The presence of both unlabeled and dye-labeled reaction components can interfere with electrokinetic injection, electrophoretic separation, and data analysis. Purification of extension products can reduce or eliminate this interference. The BigDye XTerminator Purification Kit used in this protocol sequesters cycle-sequencing reaction components such as salt ions, unincorporated dye terminators, and dNTPs.

The fragments produced by the cycle sequencing reaction are run through a long, thin tube containing a gel matrix in a process called capillary gel electrophoresis. Short fragments migrate quickly through the pores of the gel, while long fragments migrate more slowly. As each

fragment crosses the “finish line” at the end of the tube, it is illuminated by a laser, allowing the attached dye to be detected.

The smallest fragment crosses the “finish line” first, followed by the next-smallest fragment, and so forth. Thus, from the colors of fluorescent dyes registered one after another on the detector, the sequence of the original template DNA can be built up one nucleotide at a time. The data recorded by the detector consist of a series of peaks in fluorescence intensity, as shown in the chromatogram (**Figure 1**). The DNA sequence is read from the peaks in the chromatogram.

Figure 1. Protocol overview for the sequencing of template DNA followed by analysis using capillary electrophoresis. Image credit: ThermoFisher Scientific.

1.3 Technical and safety considerations

The following information should be read before starting:

- DNA quality can significantly influence the length of the fragment that can be amplified and the reproducibility of amplification from one sample to another. Even if the fragment successfully amplifies, poor quality DNA can result in decreased signal or increased background fluorescent from the sequencing reactions.
- Applied Biosystems MicroAmp Fast Optical 96-Well Reaction Plate are not compatible with the SeqStudio Genetic Analyzer. Fast plates will damage the cartridge.
- Avoid excess freeze-thaw cycles of DNA and all reagents (no more than 10). If needed, aliquot reagents into smaller amounts.
- Before each use of the kit, allow the frozen stocks to thaw on ice or at room temperature (do not heat).
- Keep thawed reagents on ice during use. Do not leave reagents at room temperature for extended periods.
- Protect fluorescent dyes from light to avoid photobleaching. Cover tubes and plates with aluminum foil.
- Mix thawed reagents thoroughly, vortex briefly, then centrifuge briefly to collect all the liquid at the bottom of each tube.
- Work in a clean area, use clean tubes/plates, and filter tips to avoid contamination.

2 Materials

Refer to the product datasheet from the supplier for further details on storage and preparation instructions.

2.1 Labware

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #
8-strip Septa for SeqStudio™ Genetic Analyzer	ThermoFisher Scientific	A35643
MicroAmp® Optical 8-Tube Strip	ThermoFisher Scientific	4316567
MicroAmp™ 96-Well Tray/Retainer Set (Adapter for 8-Tube Strip)	ThermoFisher Scientific	403081
MicroAmp™ Clear Adhesive Film	ThermoFisher Scientific	4306311
MicroAmp™ Optical 96-Well Reaction Plate	ThermoFisher Scientific	8010560
Plate Septa, 96 well	ThermoFisher Scientific	4315933

2.2 Reagents

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #	Storage temp.
BigDye XTerminator™ Purification Kit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BigDye XTerminator™ bead solution • SAM Solution 	ThermoFisher Scientific	4376486	4°C*
BigDye™ Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BigDye™ Terminator 3.1 Ready Reaction Mix • BigDye™ Terminator v1.1 & v3.1 5X Sequencing Buffer 	ThermoFisher Scientific	4337456	-20°C†
ExoSAP-IT™ Express PCR Product Cleanup Reagent	ThermoFisher Scientific	75001.1.ML	-20°C
Sequencing primer	ThermoFisher Scientific	NA (custom order)	-20°C
UltraPure™ DNase/RNase-Free Distilled Water	ThermoFisher Scientific	10977015	RT

*Do not freeze.

†Protect from light.

2.3 Equipment

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #
Applied Biosystems SeqStudio™ Genetic Analyzer	ThermoFisher Scientific	A35644
Centrifuge Eppendorf™ 5810R with swinging bucket and PCR plate adapter	Eppendorf	022627122
Microplate Vortex Mixer	Fisher Scientific	02216100
SimpliAmp™ Thermal Cycler	ThermoFisher Scientific	A24811
Sequencing Analysis Software	Non- exhaustive list in section 3.5.3	
Vortex Mixer	Fisher Scientific	88880017

3 Protocol

3.1 Cleaning Up PCR Reactions with ExoSAP-IT

Materials:

- MicroAmp Optical 96-Well Reaction Plate or 8-Tube Strip
- MicroAmp Clear Adhesive Film or 8-Tube Cap
- PCR reaction product
- ExoSAP-IT Express PCR Product Cleanup Reagent
- Thermal Cycler
- Microplate vortex mixer
- Centrifuge

Procedure:

1. Mix 5 μ L the PCR reaction product with 2 μ L of ExoSAP-IT Express reagent for a combined 7 μ L reaction volume in an 8-tube strip or 96-well reaction plate. Seal the plate or tube strip with the adhesive film or caps, respectively.
2. Vortex tube strip or plate briefly and centrifuge at 2100 rpm (1000g) for 30 seconds.
3. Run the reaction on a thermal cycler using the program described in Table 1.

Table 1. Thermal cycling program for ExoSap-IT Express PCR Product Cleanup.

Stage	Description	Temperature	Time
1	Enzyme incubation	37°C	5 min
2	Enzyme inactivation	80°C	2 min
3	Hold	4°C	Indefinite hold

4. Proceed to cycle sequencing (section 3.2) or store the treated PCR products at -20°C .
 - Treated PCR products are stable for up to 1 month at -20°C .

3.2 Cycle sequencing

Materials:

- MicroAmp Optical 96-Well Reaction Plate or 8-Tube Strip
- MicroAmp Clear Adhesive Film or 8-Tube Cap
- Purified template DNA
- Sequencing primers
- BigDye Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit
- DNase/RNase-Free Distilled Water
- Thermal Cycler
- Microplate vortex mixer
- Centrifuge

Procedure:

1. Prepare the recommended quantity of template DNA in DNase/RNase-Free Distilled Water (Table 2). The maximum volume of template DNA used per single sequencing reaction is 6 μ L.
 - The quantity of PCR product is optimized to maximize the number of primer binding sites for the BigDye reaction and is dependent upon the length and purity of the PCR product.
 - In general, higher DNA quantities give higher signal intensities.

Table 2. Recommended DNA template quantity to use in a single cycle sequencing reaction.

DNA Template	Quantity/reaction
PCR product:	
• 100–200 bp	1–3 ng
• 200–500 bp	3–10 ng
• 500–1000 bp	5–20 ng
• 1000–2000 bp	10–40 ng
• >2000 bp	20–50 ng
Single-stranded DNA	25–50 ng
Double-stranded DNA	150–300 ng
Cosmid, BAC	0.5–1.0 μ g
Bacterial genomic DNA	2–3 μ g

2. Thaw the contents of the BigDye™ Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit and sequencing primers and store on ice.

- Only a single primer is used in the sequence reaction. Forward and reverse sequencing requires 2 different reactions (1 for each primer).
3. Prepare 10 μL reaction by combining the components listed in Table 3 in an 8-tube strip or 96-well reaction plate. Seal the plate or tube strip with the adhesive film or caps, respectively.
 - Store all reagents on ice and protected from light.

Table 3. Cycle sequencing reaction components.

Component	Standard reaction (10 μL)		
	Quantity/reaction	Example Forward	Example Reverse
BigDye™ Terminator 3.1 Ready Reaction Mix	1 μL	1 μL	1 μL
BigDye™ Terminator v1.1 & v3.1 5X Sequencing Buffer	2 μL	2 μL	2 μL
Forward primer (5 μM)	5 pmol	1 μL	-
Reverse primer (5 μM)	5 pmol	-	1 μL
Purified template DNA	See Table 2	$\leq 6 \mu\text{L}$	$\leq 6 \mu\text{L}$
Deionized water (RNase/DNase-free)	Varies based on template DNA volume		
Total volume	10 μL	10 μL	10 μL

4. Vortex tube strip or plate briefly and centrifuge at 2100 rpm (1000g) for 30 seconds.
5. Run the reaction on a thermal cycler using the program described in Table 4.

Table 4. Thermal cycling program for cycle sequencing.

Stage	Description	Temperature	Time
1	Denaturation	96 °C	2 min
2	Amplification (25-30 cycles)	96 °C	20 sec
		50 °C	10 sec
		60 °C	4 min
3	Hold	4 °C	Indefinite hold

6. Proceed to purifying the sequencing reaction (section 3.3).
 - Sequencing reactions can be stored **after purification**.

3.3 Purifying the sequencing reactions

Materials:

- MicroAmp Optical 96-Well Reaction Plate or 8-Tube Strip
- MicroAmp Clear Adhesive Film or 8-Tube Cap
- Wide bore pipet tips (with an orifice >0.1 mm)
- Sequencing reaction product
- BigDye XTerminator Purification Kit
- Centrifuge
- Microplate Vortex Mixer

Procedure:

1. Vortex the bottle of BigDye XTerminator beads for 10 seconds before mixing with the SAM solution.
2. Prepare the SAM/BigDye XTerminator bead working solution by combining 45 μ L of SAM solution with 10 μ L of BigDye XTerminator bead solution per 10- μ L sequencing reaction.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Use wide bore pipet tips when pipetting the BigDye XTerminator reagent.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Avoid pipetting from the top of the liquid.
 - **IMPORTANT:** For effective BigDye XTerminator™ clean up, it is essential to keep the materials well mixed. Keep reagents on ice between pipetting steps.
3. Dispense 55 μ L of bead mix to each sample and seal the plate or tube strip with adhesive film or caps, respectively.
4. Vortex the plate or tube strip for 30 minutes at 1,800 rpm.
5. Centrifuge the plate at 1,000 \times g for 2 minutes to pellet beads.
6. Proceed to sequence analysis by capillary electrophoresis (section 3.4) or store the purified sequencing reaction at 4°C for up to 10 days or at -20°C for up to 1 month.
 - Sequencing reaction products purified with BigDye XTerminator do not require any additional resuspension solutions.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Do not heat samples or add Hi-Di Formamide when using BigDye XTerminator to purify samples.

3.4 Capillary electrophoresis

Materials:

- MicroAmp Optical 96-Well Reaction Plate or 8-Tube Strip
- MicroAmp Clear Adhesive Film or 8-Tube Cap
- Plate Septum, 96 well
- 8-strip Septum
- MicroAmp 96-Well Tray/Retainer Set (Adapter for 8-Tube Strip)
- Purified sequencing reaction
- Applied Biosystems SeqStudio Genetic Analyzer

Procedure:

3.4.1 Prepare the instrument

1. Log in to the SeqStudio Genetic Analyzer instrument.
2. Select **Settings**, and then **Consumable status**. Review the information on the Consumable status screen (**Figure 2**) to ensure that a sufficient number of injections are remaining for the cartridge and cathode buffer and that they have not exceeded their expiry date and time.

Figure 2. Consumable status screen. Image credit: ThermoFisher Scientific.

3.4.2 Create or modify a plate setup from the Plate Manager

1. Log in to computer.
2. Open the **Plate Manager** on desktop screen.
3. In the **Plate Setup** screen, select **Create** or **Open a plate setup** (.PSM file).
4. In **Plate Properties** screen (**Figure 3**), enter plate properties:
 - Plate name
 - Owner (optional)
 - Plate setup security: Share
 - Application type: **Sequencing**
 - Sequencing analysis settings: **Default analysis settings**
5. Select **Next**.

The screenshot shows the 'Plate Properties' window in the Plate Manager (PM) software. The window has a header with 'PM' and tabs for 'Properties', 'Plate', and 'Run'. The 'Plate Properties' section includes the following fields and options:

- Plate name:** Text input field containing 'Plate 20190402_093003'.
- Barcode:** Text input field containing '(optional)'.
- Owner:** Text input field containing '(optional)'.
- Plate setup security:** A dropdown menu set to 'Shared'. Below it, a legend explains: 'Hidden: Only you can view or access the plate setup on the instrument. Shared: Other users may view or edit the plate setup on the instrument.'
- Application type:** A dropdown menu set to 'Sequencing'.
- Sequencing analysis settings:** A dropdown menu set to 'Default analysis settings' with a 'Setting Details' link next to it.

On the right side, there is a checkbox labeled 'I am analyzing my data with Sanger variant analysis software.' which is currently unchecked. Below this checkbox, a note states: 'You will be prompted to assign an amplicon and specimen to each well. This will automatically organize your files in a way that is compatible with the analysis software.'

At the bottom right of the window, there is a blue 'Next' button.

Figure 3. Plate properties screen. Image credit: ThermoFisher Scientific.

- In the **Verify and Assign Samples** screen (**Figure 4**), assign samples names.
 - Each set of 4 wells within a column on the plate is referred to as an injection group.
 - IMPORTANT:** Sequencing reactions must be analysed on the instrument in multiples of 4 to avoid wasting expensive reagents.

Figure 4. Verify and Assign Samples screen. Image credit: ThermoFisher Scientific.

- Select a **Dye Set** for the injection group: **Z_BigDye™ Terminator v3.1**.

8. Select a **Run Module** for the injection group as described in Table 5.

Table 5. Sequencing run modules.

Run module	Expected read length	Approximately time
ShortSeq	Up to 350bp	30 min
ShortSeq_BDX		
MediumSeq	Up to 500bp	45 min
MediumSeq_BDX		
LongSeq	Up to 800bp	<2 hours
LongSeq_BDX		

- **IMPORTANT:** The .BDX run modules adjust the injection height to remove only the supernatant containing the purified dye-labeled extension products and to avoid touching the beads pellet. Use .BDX run modules if you prepare samples with BigDye XTerminator Purification Kit.
- Use non-BDX run modules if the purified supernatant is transferred to a new reaction plate (i.e. there are no bead pellets), or for sequencing reactions purified with other methods.
- If running the LongSeq modules, analyze a maximum of 48 samples on a plate. Additional samples will take more than 24 hours and the samples can degrade.

9. Select **Next**.

10. In the **Save the plate setup** dialog box, modify the Plate name and file name as needed.

- All files names should be suffixed with a date and time stamp.

11. Select **Save** to generate a **.PSM file** that can be opened from the desktop (SeqStudio_Data > Plates), a network drive, or a USB drive, and run on the instrument.

- By default, .PSM files are saved in the folder SeqStudio_Data > Plates on the desktop.

3.4.3 Load samples

1. If samples are prepared with BigDye XTerminator Purification Kit, ensure that beads are pelleted before loading.
 - Sequencing reactions plate or tube-strip are analysed in columns as shown in **Figure 5**. The default injection order is: A1–D1, E1–H1, A2–D2, E2–H2....A12–D12, E12–H12.

Figure 5. Default injection order. Image credit: ThermoFisher Scientifics

2. Place a plate or 8-strip septum onto the centrifuged sequencing reaction plate or tube-strip. Use a 96-well tray/retainer set for 8-tube strip (**Figure 6**).
 - Align the holes of the septum with the plate wells or tubes.
 - Press the septum gently until it is inserted into position in each well or tube.

Figure 6. Placing of septum onto the plate and 8-tube strip using a 96-well tray/retainer set. Image credit: ThermoFisher Scientifics

3. In the instrument **Home** screen, select **Eject plate** and then open the instrument door when prompted.

4. Press the release button on the autosampler (**Figure 7**) to open the lid.
5. Place the plate or tube assembly firmly in the autosampler.
6. Close the autosampler lid by pressing down on the center of the lid or pressing down on both sides of the lid with equal pressure until the lid clicks shut.
7. Touch **Retract plate**, and then close the instrument door.

Figure 7. Autosampler. Image credit: ThermoFisher Scientifics

- Samples are stable for 16–24 hours on the instrument.

3.4.4 Select a plate setup and start a run

1. In the instrument **Home** screen, select Setup run.
 2. Under Network Drive > Plates, open the desired plate setup file (.PSM).
 3. Verify that settings are correct and that the data will be saved under Network drive > Instrument.
 4. Select **Start run**.
- In the **Home** screen of the instrument, view the run time information and the status for each capillary (**Figure 8**).

Figure 8. Run time information and status for each capillary in the home screen. Image credit: ThermoFisher Scientific

3.4.5 Unload the plate or the tube assembly

1. When the run is complete, in the instrument **Home** screen, select **Eject plate** and then open the instrument door when prompted.
2. Press the release button on the autosampler to open the lid.
3. Remove the plate or tube assembly.
4. Close the autosampler lid.
5. Touch Retract plate, then close the instrument door.
6. Remove septa from the plate or tubes, rinse with water and let it dry.
 - Septa can be re-used after autoclaving.

3.5 View and analyze sequencing data

Materials:

- Applied Biosystems SeqStudio Genetic Analyzer
- SeqStudio sample files (.AB1)
- Sequencing analysis software

Procedure:

3.5.1 View results on the instrument

1. In the instrument **Home** screen, select View Results.
2. Select List view.
3. Select an injection group.
4. View the results in the Run Result Details screen.
5. Select a sample file (.AB1) and select View data to display the analyzed electropherogram for the sample (**Figure 9**).

- ① Size Quality bars and values:
 - ■ QV \geq 20
 - ■ QV 10–19
 - ■ QV <10
- ② Bases—Mixed bases are displayed in red (if they exceed the Mixed base threshold specified in analysis settings).
- ③ Trace color hide/show—Touch to open, then touch a color to hide or show.
- ④ Analyzed trace
- ⑤ Thumbnail trace—Drag the center of the pane in the thumbnail trace to display another trace area in the top pane. Drag the right or left handle of the pane to zoom horizontally.
- ⑥ Zoom tools—Touch to open.
- ⑦ Next trace tool—Touch to view the raw trace or EPT for the well.

Figure 9. Sequence analysis electropherogram view on the instrument. Credit Image: ThermoFisher Scientific

3.5.2 Export results from the instrument

1. In the instrument **Home** screen, select Settings > Run history.
2. Select one or more plates from the Run History table.
3. Select Export.
4. Select a storage location (USB drive).

5. Select Export.

- Sequencing experiments use base calling (the algorithms and settings required to determine the fragment base sequences) and generate an .AB1 file for each sample. A sequencing file (.AB1) and plate quality check (QC) report (.CSV and .PDF) are automatically exported to the folder **SeqStudio_Data > Data > Plate name** on the desktop.

3.5.3 Analyse Data

For each sample, open the .AB1 file in the sequencing analysis software in order to analyze the data, display sequencing electropherogram (**Figure 10**), edit, save, and print sample files.

- Examples of sequencing analysis software:
 - Sequencing Analysis Software - Applied Biosystems (Windows)
 - SeqScape Software - Applied Biosystems (Windows)
 - Variant Reporter Software – Applied Biosystems (Windows)
 - SnapGene Viewer - GSL Biotech (Windows / MAC / Linux)
 - Chromaseq - Maddison, D.R., & W.P. Maddison. (Windows / MAC / Linux)
 - Genome Compiler – Genome Compiler (Windows / MAC)

Figure 10. Electropherogram view on Sequencing Analysis Software – Applied Biosystems.